

The prevalence of direct and indirect sequelae of conventional complete dentures in an Iranian population

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Abstract

Background: The purpose of this study was to determine the frequency of the direct and indirect sequelae caused by wearing conventional complete dentures and investigation of their relationship with these factors: gender, age, educational level, systemic diseases, medications, xerostomia, the person who made the denture, chief complaint of patients, duration of denture wearing (24 hours a day), cleaning methods of dentures and condition of the old dentures.

Materials and Methods: Forty-seven patients with old conventional complete dentures, who referred to dentistry faculty of Kurdistan University of Medical Sciences, participated in this study. Data were obtained by using a questionnaire-interview and clinical examination and were analyzed with chi-squared test ($P < 0.05$).

Results: 3 denture related lesions showed in 42.55% of the patients and only 2 patients did not have any lesions. Resorbed residual ridge (27.7%) was the most common and hyper keratosis (2.7%) was the uncommon sequelae. The Denture Irritation Hyperplasia (DIH) was significantly higher in patients with lower educational level. Denture stomatitis was the most common mucosal lesion in the participants who suffered from xerostomia.

Conclusion: The patients should be educated about the importance of periodic examination in order to diagnose early mucosal lesions and repairing the dentures.

Keywords: direct sequel, indirect sequel, conventional complete denture, denture-induced oral lesion

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INTRODUCTION

The term edentulism reflects an organ deficiency that is seen in elderly people generally and has a deep effect on quality of life (Jeganathan, Payne 1993). In spite of a decline in the number of edentulous patients, still great majority of edentulous people will have to rely on conventional complete dentures (Carlsson, Omar 2006). A successful prosthesis is comprised of an aesthetic restoration, having good functional qualities, allowing comfortable and confident use. Informing the patient about the method of denture cleaning and denture wearing during 24 hours a day for having a healthy mucosa is necessary (Cook, 1991).

Conventional complete denture leads to direct and indirect sequelae in the oral cavity (**Table 1**). Direct mucosal reaction often results from mechanical irritation along with an accumulation of microbial plaque on the

dentures following an infrequent toxic or allergic reaction to the denture material. Moreover, long-term and continuous denture wearing also may have a negative effect on residual ridge form due to progressive alveolar bone resorption. In addition, wearing complete dentures that function poorly and impair masticatory function could be a negative factor with regard to maintenance of adequate muscle function and nutritional status, particularly in older people (Petersen, Yamamoto 2005, Jaikittivong, Aneksuk, Langlais 2010, Coelho, Zucoloto, Lopes, 2000, Budtz-Jørgensen, 2000).

The prevalence of direct mucosal reaction and denture-induced oral lesions has been reported in several studies. In the studies conducted from 1971 to

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Table 1. Direct and Indirect Sequelae Caused by Complete Dentures

Direct sequelae	Indirect sequelae
Traumatic ulcer	Atrophy of masticatory muscles
Denture Irritation Hyperplasia (DIH)	
Denture stomatitis	
Angular cheilitis	
Flabby ridge Hyper keratosis	
Residual ridge resorption	

2014, these direct mucosal reactions have been evaluated. The mean prevalence of these lesions included: traumatic ulcers 15.55%, Denture Irritation Hyperplasia (DIH) 20.67%, Denture stomatitis 35.4%, angular cheilitis 17.2%, flabby ridge 17.55%, and severe residual ridge resorption 32%. Denture stomatitis was the most common lesion evaluated in these studies (Sheppard, Schwartz, Sheppard. 1971; Budtz-Jørgensen, 1981; Peltola, Raustia, Salonen. 1997; Nevalainen, Närhi, Ainamo. 1997; MacEntee, Glick, Stolar. 1998; Jaikkittivong, Aneksuk, Langlais. 2002; Espinoza et al. 2003; Shulman, Beach, Rivera-Hidalgo 2004; Zisis, Yannikakis, Harrison. 2006; Figueiral et al. 2007; Emami et al. 2008; Marcos-Arias et al. 2009; Baran, Nalçacı 2009. Gendreau, Loewy 2011; Evren et al. 2011; Martori, et al. 2014)

This study was conducted to determine the exact prevalence of orals lesions among denture wearers and to find out any correlation between these lesions and risk factors associated with development of these lesions for example gender, age, educational level, systemic diseases, medications, subjective feeling of dry mouth (xerostomia), the person who made the denture, chief complaint of patients about the old dentures, duration of denture wearing (24 hours a day), cleaning methods of dentures and condition of the old dentures.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was a cross sectional (descriptive-analytical) study. The sample size was estimated according to the ratio of the denture-induced lesions that was equal to 0.15 (Martori et al. 2014).and the following formula:

$$n = \frac{z_{1-\alpha/2}^2 \times p \times q}{d^2}$$

And the error level which was 0.1. The 47 subjects (26 males and 21 females) with determined inclusion criteria were selected from the population of patients referring to the Department of Prosthodontics, Kurdistan University of Medical Sciences, Dentistry Faculty. The objectives and methods of the study was explained to patients and informed written consents were obtained. This research with the ethics number: IR.MUK.REC.1396/246 was approved at the ethics committee of Kurdistan University of Medical Sciences in Dec 5th 2017.

Table 2. Prevalence of the Direct and Indirect Sequelae Caused by Conventional Complete Dentures

Type of lesion	prevalence	Percentage (%)
Traumatic ulcer	14	9.4
Epulis fissuratum	8	5.4
Angular cheilitis	14	9.4
Mastication muscles atrophy	26	17.5
Residual ridge resorption	41	27.7
Flabby ridge	22	14.8
Hyper keratosis	4	2.7
Denture stomatitis	Type I	5
	Type II	5
	Type III	9

Inclusion criteria

1. Patients used conventional complete denture for at least past one year and referred to replace them with new one.
2. Patients weren't happy with their previous denture.

Exclusion criteria

1. The patients, who had the lesions that were non-related to denture.
2. The patients who hadn't old denture or lost it.

A questionnaire was designed included demographic and social data, medical and dental history, intra-oral and denture examination, the person who made the denture, chief complaint of patients about the old dentures, duration of denture wearing (24 hours a day), cleaning methods of denture and condition of the old dentures. The validity of the questionnaire was evaluated and the Cronbach's alpha test used to confirm reliability which was calculated by 0.83.

The Single clinician completed the questionnaires by asking the patients and along with the clinical examination.

The clinician did clinical examinations to diagnose the denture-induced lesions, like traumatic ulcers, DIH, denture stomatitis, angular cheilitis, flabby ridge, hyperkeratosis, residual ridge resorption, and atrophy of masticatory muscles.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS 21. In order to describe the qualitative variables, frequency and percentages were used. Central indicators and dispersion were used to describe the quantitative variables. For dependent variables, the difference between two distributions was tested by the Chi-squared test. The level of statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS

In this study, the prevalence of sequelae caused by wearing complete denture are shown in **Table 2**. The age range of the patients was 38 to 84 years old (mean=57.53). Among 47 patients, 55.3% were male (n=26) and 44.7% were female (n=21). No statistically significant correlation was found between the age and

Fig. 1. Distribution of educational Levels of Participants

Fig. 2. The person who made the denture

Table 3. The prevalence of systemic diseases

Systemic disease	prevalence	Percentage (%)
Renal disease	3	6.3
Diabetes mellitus type II	3	6.3
Hypertension	9	19.14
Immunologic disease	1	2.13
Cardiovascular disease	5	10.6
Cancer	3	6.3
Osteoarthritis	3	6.3

sequelae caused by wearing complete dentures except for atrophy of masticatory muscles ($p < 0.05$). The atrophy of masticatory muscles was significantly higher in aged patients. No statistically significant correlation was found between the gender and sequelae. The educational levels of the patients are shown in Fig. 1. No statistically significant correlation was found between the educational level and sequelae except for DIH. The DIH was significantly higher in patients with lower educational level. Overall, 57.44% of participants were found to have some type of systemic disease. The prevalence of systemic diseases has shown in Table 3. No statistically significant correlation was found between the systemic diseases and sequelae. A total of 29.78% of participants used medications, that antihypertensive medications were the most common medications (57.2%). No statistically significant correlation was found between medication use and sequelae. Overall, 31.9% of patients had reported xerostomia. No statistically significant correlation was found between the xerostomia and sequelae.

The information about the person who made the denture is reported in Fig. 2. No statistically significant

Table 4. The methods for cleaning dentures

Methods for cleaning dentures	prevalence	Percentage (%)
Toothbrush and toothpaste	19	40.4
Toothbrush and liquid soap or dishwashing liquid	10	21.2
Toothbrush and water	8	17.02
Sodium hypochlorite	7	14.9
Toothbrush and washing powder	4	8.5
Toothbrush and salt	9	19.1
Vinegar	1	2.1
No particular materials	10	21.2

correlation was found between the person who made the denture and sequelae.

Poor fit was the most common chief complaint of patients about the old dentures (25.5%), followed by teeth flattening (23.4%), denture fracture (12.8%), traumatic ulcer (10.6%), the age of the denture > 15 years (8.5%), plaque and stain in denture (4.2%), the sense of suffocation (2.1%). No statistically significant correlation was found between the chief complaint of patients about the old dentures and sequelae.

The average of denture wearing duration was equal to 19.76 hours. The minimum and maximum denture wearing duration was equal to 2 hours and 24 hours, respectively. No statistically significant correlation was found between the denture wearing duration and sequelae.

The methods for cleaning dentures are shown in Table 4. A statistically significant correlation was found between the use of toothbrush and toothpaste and the use of toothbrush and water and DIH ($p < 0.05$).

Table 5. The disadvantages of old dentures

Disadvantage	prevalence	Percentage (%)
Low VDO	38	80.8
High VDO	5	21.2
Attrition of the teeth	40	85.1
Presence of stain	40	85.1
Presence of plaque	7	14.9
Decrease in the retention and resistance	40	85.1
Detachment of the teeth	7	14.9
Incorrect occlusion	24	51.06
Under flanges	16	34.04
Over flanges	12	25.5
Fractured denture	15	31.9
Other problems	5	10.6

The condition of the old dentures was shown in **Table 5**. A statistically significant correlation was found between these factors ($p < 0.05$).

The loss of VDO and angular cheilitis,

The decrease in the retention and resistance and resorbed residual ridge,

The detachment of the teeth and traumatic ulcer,

The incorrect occlusion and flabby ridge,

The over flanges and epulis fissuratum,

The over flanges and hyperkeratosis.

DISCUSSION

This study evaluated the sequelae caused by wearing complete dentures and some related factors in the patients who referred to Faculty of Dentistry, Kurdistan University of medical sciences.

Resorbed residual ridge was the most common sequel caused by wearing complete denture was in this study. After tooth extraction and placement of complete denture, alveolar remodeling and reduction will happen. This high frequency can result from tooth loss at young ages. In other studies, some systemic diseases are considered as risk factors for occurrence of residual ridge resorption. Also, the quality of previous dentures is another factor resulting in ridge resorption (Xie et al. 1997).

In this study, mastication muscles atrophy was the second sequel. This sequel is an indirect sequel. It is essential that oral function in complete denture wearers is maintained throughout life. This depends on the skeletal muscular force and the facility by which the patient is able to coordinate oral functional movement during mastication. Maximal bite forces tend to decrease in older patients. In the completely edentulous patients, placement of implants is usually followed by an improvement of the masticatory function and an increase in maximal occlusal forces (Ikebe, et al. 2005).

Flabby ridge was the third sequel. This result is lower than some studies (Mandali et al. 2011), and higher than some other studies (Coelho, Sousa, Dare 2004; Turker et al. 2010). Desjardins et al reported that the etiology of flabby ridge is multifactorial. It could be related to age, lack of nourishment, disease, action of toxins, pressure and interference with neural innervation, but old age and

pressure are encountered as the most common ones (Desjardins, Tolman. 1974).

Denture stomatitis was the fourth sequel. The prevalence of stomatitis reported in this study is close to some studies. This prevalence in some studies was higher (Gaur, et al. 2015). In these two studies the denture stomatitis was the most common sequel of complete denture wearing, but in our study the denture stomatitis was the fourth one. Denture stomatitis type III had high frequency than denture stomatitis types I, II. In other studies, the prevalence of different types of denture stomatitis was changeable (Shah, Ahmad 2011; Atashrazm, Sadri. 2013).

Traumatic ulcer and angular cheilitis (9.4%), DIH (5.4%), hyper keratosis (2.7%) had lowest prevalence. Considering traumatic ulcer, some studies reported a higher prevalence, which ranges from 15% to 92% (Moskona, Kaplan. 1995). Other studies reported a lower prevalence (3.5%-8%) (Dorey, et al. 1985). In some studies, angular cheilitis had a higher prevalence. In other studies, angular cheilitis had a lower prevalence, which ranges from 2.3% to 8.9%. In some studies, DIH had a higher prevalence, which ranges from 7% to 18.51%. In other studies, DIH had a lower prevalence (Axéll, 1976).

In this study, the prevalence of sequelae caused by wearing complete denture was high. After placement of the dentures, it is the responsibility of dentist to instruct the patients regarding how to keep their mouth healthy and to schedule post-insertion recall visits.

Although no substantial evidence is reported, malignant lesions such as squamous cell carcinoma and gingival carcinoma have been associated with chronic irritation. Therefore, dentists can play a significant role in educating patients and in the early diagnosis of malignant lesions in denture wearers (Mubarak, et al. 2015).

In this study, 55.3% were male and 44.7% were female. No statistically significant correlation was found between the gender and sequelae caused by wearing complete dentures. This result is similar to that reported in some studies.

The age range of the patients was 38 to 84 years old (mean=57.53). No statistically significant correlation was found between the age and sequelae caused by wearing complete dentures except for atrophy of masticatory muscles. The atrophy of masticatory muscles was significantly higher in aged patients. This correlation in other studies was significant for denture stomatitis and traumatic ulcers, that increase along with increasing age of patients.

No statistically significant correlation was found between the educational level and sequelae except for DIH. The DIH was significantly higher in patients with lower educational level. DIH occurs around the borders or flanges of an ill-fitting complete denture. Initially there may be a small ulcer, but as the flange continues to

irritate the tissue, a productive inflammation develops (Miller, 1977; De Arruda Paes-Junior et al. 2010). A study reported an indirect relation between denture stomatitis, traumatic ulcers and educational level. Another study reported that the frequency of all denture-related lesions is increased with the length of denture use. Therefore, DIH can be related to the lower educational level and long-time denture use. In other studies, this correlation was not significant.

No statistically significant correlation was found between the systemic diseases and sequelae caused by wearing complete dentures. This result is similar to some studies. Other studies reported that there is a statistically significant correlation between some systemic diseases and sequelae caused by wearing complete dentures (Dundar, Kal 2007).

No statistically significant correlation was found between the medication use and xerostomia and sequelae. Denture stomatitis was the most common mucosal lesion in the participants who suffered from xerostomia. This result is similar to some studies. In other studies, there was a positive correlation between medication use and some sequelae of conventional complete denture. This relationship may be found as a result of oral mucosa becoming more vulnerable to mechanical damage accompanied with the xerostomic effects of drugs (Guggenheimer, Moore 2003).

Considering the person who made the denture, the prevalence of sequelae was higher in patients whose dentures were made by denturist. However, this increase was not statistically significant. In many countries denturists have become a main part of the health service in competition with dentists. There is little clinical evidence that complete dentures provided by denturists pose a risk to older people. A cooperative and mutually supportive relationship between dentists and denturists could improve oral health and comfort in the aged patients.

No statistically significant correlation was found between the denture wearing duration (24 hours a day) and sequelae. There are controversies between different studies. Some studies reported that the patients who wore their dentures day and night did not have any

more stomatitis or hyperplastic changes than those who took them out at night. Other studies reported that continuous and nocturnal wear of prosthesis increases the frequency of denture stomatitis (Wilson 1998).

The use of toothbrush and toothpaste was the most common method for cleaning dentures. Our result is similar to some studies. Patients often think that ordinary teeth cleaning methods are suitable for denture cleaning. Denture cleaning methods may influence the condition of dentures, and pigmentation and abrasions in dentures occur due to the use of toothpaste or toothbrush (De Castellucci Barbosa, et al. 2008). In this study, a statistically significant correlation was found between the use of toothbrush and toothpaste and the use of toothbrush and water with DIH. Some similar studies reported no significant relationship between denture stomatitis and hygienic habits (BarBeau, et al. 2003). Other studies reported that some denture-induced oral lesions were associated with poor denture hygiene.

CONCLUSION

The frequency of direct and indirect sequelae caused by wearing complete denture was high. In order to improve oral health status of complete denture wearers, these measures should be carried out:

1. Informing the patients regarding the need for frequent follow-up for diagnosis of early mucosal lesions and repairing the denture.
2. Instructing the patients regarding the method for denture cleaning and denture wearing duration (24 hours a day).
3. Increasing the cooperation between dentists and denturists in the process of complete denture construction.

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